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Satellite Remote Sensing of Ocean Conditions - Fronts and Eddies

Metocean Project
Norwegian Deepwater Programme

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A/S Norske Shell

Investigators:
Stein Sandven
Kjell Kloster
and
Torill Hamre

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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Edv. Griegsvei 3a,
N-5037 Solheimsviken, Bergen
NORWAY.

Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50

e-mail: administrasjonen@nrsc.no

Internet: <http://www.nrsc.no/>

*a non-profit environmental research
center affiliated with the university of
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Executive Summary

The study area for the Norwegian Deep Water Programme is characterised by a complicated bathymetry where the Norwegian Atlantic Current dominates the ocean circulation. The mesoscale variability of this current, including meanders, eddies and fronts, is important to investigate for offshore activities.

In the last decade, use of satellite remote sensing techniques for observation of meteorological and oceanographical phenomena has developed rapidly. The Nansen Center has played an important role in this development in Norwegian waters. The most useful remote sensing techniques (altimeter and SAR) are based on microwaves which enable observations of ocean surface processes and phenomena independent of cloud and light conditions. The main advantage of satellite data is the capability of synoptic observations over large areas, and by coordination with available in situ measurements, optimal data sets can be obtained to characterize meteorological and oceanographical conditions in any ocean region.

The study has focused on the use of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data from the European ERS-2 satellite to map the location of surface features relative to changes in bathymetry, and on using Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data from the NOAA 12 and 14 satellites to map sea surface temperature, including temperature fronts and eddies. The report describes the main eddy and frontal features observed in these satellite data in the period from November 1996 to June 1998. A total of 33 SAR images and 6 AVHRR images were obtained from the archives of Tromsø Satellite Station. The SAR images were selected for low wind conditions which allowed observation of surface eddy and frontal signature. AVHRR images were selected from days when the study area was cloudfree.

The main results of the image analysis are as follows:

- Ocean fronts were seen in about 75% of the SAR images, with a typical length of 20-40km. In about half of these images, the front were oriented in 1-2 predominant directions (NW-SE and SW-NW).
- Current patterns due to slicks were observed in nearly 60% of the SAR images. The current patterns, which showed the mesoscale flow field, were most frequently found from April to August, and had no predominant direction.
- Eddies were observed in about 75% of the SAR images. Typical horizontal scale of the eddies was 10-30km, and the rotation was cyclonic for most of the eddies. In one case the mean propagation speed over a 3-day period could be estimated to 18cm/s for one cyclonic eddy. Near simultaneous observations of eddies in SAR and AVHRR images were also made in 2 cases.
- Relating the satellite data analysis to the bottom topography in the study area showed that the maximum occurrence of fronts and eddies is found northwest of Stad and along the shelf break from 62.5°N to 65°N and from 66.5°N to 67.5°N.

Analysis of satellite SAR data in combination with in situ current data will give more detailed information about eddies and other current phenomena in the study area. Altimeter data have been analysed for ocean currents in the study area. AVHRR data are only useful in days with cloudfree conditions which occur rarely in the study area. In the last part of this study, in situ current measurements and model simulations in the Metocean Project will be used to analyse and interpret the satellite radar data, and to assess the overall capability of satellite data to provide useful information about ocean currents.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The study region off the coast of mid-Norway from approximately 62° to 65°N is characterised by a complicated bathymetry combined with ocean currents and fronts. The dominant feature is the Norwegian Atlantic Current which have high mesoscale variability, generating meanders and eddies in the frontal zone. This area is also exposed to severe wave conditions, where waves interact with the currents, creating complex and unpredictable sea state conditions.

Satellite remote sensing techniques for observation of meteorological and oceanographical phenomena have developed rapidly in the last 10 years. For many years satellite data were limited to optical and infrared sensors which could mainly be used to observe clouds and surface temperature as part of the global meteorological observations system. With the development of microwave radar techniques it is now possible to observe and quantify several processes and phenomena at the sea surface such as waves, winds, fronts, eddies and current structures.

The main advantage of satellite data is the capability of synoptic observations over large areas. When these synoptic observations are coordinated with in situ wind, waves and current measurements optimal data sets can be obtained to characterize meteorological and oceanographical conditions over large ocean areas.

The Nansen Center has long experience in development and application of marine remote sensing methods off the coast of Norway. In the last 10-15 years several major oceanographical investigations have been coordinated by the Nansen Center where use of remote sensing has been an important component. The most important investigations are: NORSEX 79 north of Svalbard, the coastal eddy experiment off the west coast of Norway in 1986, the NORCSEX experiments on Haltenbanken in 1988 and 1991 (Haugan et al. 1991), and COASTWATCH 1995 off the southwest coast of Norway (Johannessen et al., 1996b).

The development of microwave remote sensing techniques at the Nansen Center has been prioritized because microwaves penetrate clouds and are considered to be most important in Norwegian areas because they are not affected by the high frequency of cloud occurrence. Methods to observe surface winds, slicks, fronts and eddies from SAR have been developed and applied in a number of studies (Johannessen et al., 1994; Johannessen et al., 1996a; Samuel et al., 1996 a; Johannessen et al., 1996b, 1997a). In Samuel (1993) and Samuel et al. (1994), radar altimeter data have been used to map eddy kinetic energy in the Norwegian Sea, and, in combination with numerical model results, to study the variability of the inflow of Atlantic water into the Norwegian Sea. Use of satellite data in operational oceanography within EuroGOOS has been analysed and published by Johannessen et al. (1997b).

The study has focused on the use of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data, AVHRR data, and comparison of current and eddy observations in the images with estimates from altimeter data and in situ measurements from moorings. SAR images with high resolution (down to 10 m) can be used to map surface waves, wave lengths, propagation, refraction and wave spectra.

SAR data also has a unique capability to detect fronts, eddies and current structures and to quantify surface wind field with high resolution. The most important SAR satellites in operation are ERS-2 and RADARSAT. SAR data from ERS-2 are available in 100 km wide stripes, while RADARSAT SAR data are available in several modes with different resolution and swath widths, up to a maximum of 500 km.

Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data from NOAA 12 and 14 are used to map sea surface temperature, including temperature fronts and eddies. The AVHRR data used in combination with SAR data can improve the possibility to observe fronts and eddies. SAR data is particularly useful since SAR data penetrate clouds which limits the use of AVHRR data.

1.2 Study objectives

The specific objectives of this work are:

1. To provide an overview of available ERS LRI (Low Resolution Image) data showing current features off the coast of Mid-Norway.
2. To identify and characterise these features, using AVHRR images as an additional source of information.

The work is part of the METOCEAN meteorological and oceanographic program to investigate environmental conditions in deeper waters off Norwegian shelf. The study area is centered roughly on the continental slope between 62°N and 68°N, where a number of deep water blocks are situated (Møre Vest, Ormen Lange, Helland-Hansen, Gjallar Ridge, Vema/Nyk) (Fig. 1.1).

The report describes main eddy and frontal features observed in these satellite data in the period from November 1996 to June 1998.

To obtain a better understanding of the oceanographic conditions in the study area, in situ measurements of ocean currents can be compared with the current features found in satellite images. A number of in situ current measurements by moored current meters have been made, in and near these blocks in various time periods over the last years. At selected positions along a line from Svinøy Fyr (62.3°N, 5.3°E) to the position 64.5°N, 0°E, current measurements have been made on a regular basis for several years by the Geophysical Institute at the University of Bergen. Also altimeter data have been investigated for ocean currents (Samuel et al., 1997). In the final stage of the study all these data will be compared to give the best possible picture of the currents conditions in the area.

The report is organised as follows: Chapter 2 contains a general description of the infrared and microwave satellite images used in this study, with emphasis on what parameters can be measured, temporal and spatial coverage and other properties affecting the use of such data. Next, in Chapter 3, two selected earlier works on current front observations in SAR imagery are discussed. In Chapter 4, the procedure for searching and selecting satellite imagery for this study is described, followed by the analysis of the chosen data sets (Chapter 5). Results of the study is discussed in Chapter 6, before the final conclusions are drawn in Chapter 7.

Figure 1.1 Overview of deep water areas. The Svinøy section is marked with a thick dashed line.

2. Properties of the satellite images

2.1 Basic measured variables

Two different types of satellited images have been used in this study: (1) AVHRR¹ data, and (2) SAR² data. Under favorable conditions, signatures of current-related features at the sea surface can be observed in both image types, which are taken in the thermal infrared (TIR) and microwave (μ -wave) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum, respectively.

In the thermal infrared region, the temperature of the upper millimeter of the water is measured. This “skin temperature” is usually considered to be representative for the bulk temperature of the ocean surface layer. Water masses in the surface layer separated by temperature fronts can therefore be identified in AVHRR images in cloud free conditions, showing the position of the associated current shear fronts or eddies. This phenomenon has been observed in previous experiments off the Norwegian coast (Johannessen et al., 1989, Johannessen et al., 1996b). If consecutive images taken with a short time interval are available, for instance once per day, a time-averaged current may be derived by feature tracking.

In SAR images, data are created by the return signal which is a fraction of the emitted signal from the SAR. This fraction, called backscatter coefficient or sigma-zero, is mainly determined by the wave roughness on a scale around 6 cm of the water surface, which is close to the wavelength of the C-band SAR instrument onboard the ERS-2 satellite. Waves on this scale are called capillary waves or Bragg waves, and are caused by the near-surface wind. The capillary waves and thus the backscatter signal are modulated by many sea surface processes, such as long ocean waves, precipitation, internal waves, current shear, current divergence and convergence, and by slicks of surface material of various kinds (oil spill, natural film, ice, etc.). There are two main mechanisms that make ocean fronts and eddies visible in SAR images:

- The wind-driven capillary waves will change amplitude and/or direction at a current shear/ convergence/ divergence front. The resulting change in backscatter will show these fronts as dark or bright lines in the radar image (Johannessen et al., 1996a). In many cases a current front is also associated with a sea surface temperature (SST) front. Different SST has impact on the boundary layer stability which may induce a change in the background backscatter from one side of the front to the other.
- Surface slicks will often decrease capillary wave amplitude in low-wind conditions (the oil on water effect). If slicks containing organic material is found in the shear and convergence zones in a current front or in an eddy, they will act as tracer of the position of these zones, and especially of the form of the eddy. This phenomenon is shown in e.g. ESA's SAR ocean feature catalogue (Johannessen et al., 1994). The background brightness is normally uniform for these slicks, but since it depends on the local wind, it may fall below instrument threshold, making the slick effect invisible in the lowest wind parts of the image.

¹ AVHRR - Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer.

² SAR - Synthetic Aperture Radar

Capillary wave-change-by-current and slick material concentrations will generate backscatter changes which identify the position of the current features. The speed of the surface currents cannot be derived, but time series of images can show displacement of fronts and eddies. In practice ERS SAR data are not feasible for feature tracking since the shortest revisit period at 65°N is 3 days. Even with the one day revisit time, which was demonstrated during the ERS tandem operation from September 1995 to June 1996, it has been found that the same feature can be identified in only 20% of the cases studied (Sandven et al., 1997).

Two other methods of deriving the relative current speed from SAR data have been attempted, using: (1) the wave refraction at a current boundary, and (2) the amplitude of the backscatter change at the current boundary (O'Donnel et al., 1998). These methods are at the research level and difficult to apply for practical estimation of current speeds.

2.2 Temporal and spatical coverage of the satellite images

The great advantage of using satellite images for observing ocean surface features, is the synoptic (within minutes) coverage of large areas. ERS SAR images cover 100km wide swaths, and AVHRR images 2,000km swaths. An important issue in use of satellite images is how to obtain optimal sampling in space and time. The data used in this project come from near-polar orbiting satellites, such as NOAA-12, NOAA-14 and ERS-2, where three factors determine the mean time interval, T_m , between data coverage of an observation position:

1. The swath width of the instrument: T_m decreases with increasing swath width.
2. The latitude of the observation position: T_m decreases towards the poles (roughly proportional to cosine of the latitude).
3. The operational schedule, or how often the instrument is turned "on": T_m decreases with increasing instrument "on-time".

The AVHRR scanning radiometers onboard the NOAA-12 and NOAA-14 are always turned on and cover the equator 2 times per day, but more frequently at higher latitudes. At every pass, the instrument swath covers an area more than 2,500 km wide, but the performance is reduced at the swath edges. A scene is about 2,000 km wide and approximately 1,600 km long, centered on the satellite subtrack. At Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), the majority of the AVHRR scenes of interest are processed to images and archived for later distribution.

The temporal and spatial sampling is much more sparse for the SAR onboard the ERS-2 satellite. Typical coverage in 3 days is shown in Figure 2.1. With a swath width of only 100 km, a given position at 65°N can only be imaged every six days on average if the instrument is always turned on. At present, the instrument is turned on and off by command, and is generally turned off for northbound (ascending) passes. This means the average revisit interval is 12 days, if all descending passes are turned on. As the turn-on time is also limited by power constraints and largely determined by demands from customers, descending passes may also have the SAR instrument turned off. Consequently, the mean sampling interval will be further lengthened.

A SAR scene 100 km x 100 km, and is centered 300km to the right of the satellite track. Finally, only the SAR scenes that have been processed at TSS are archived as digital files and in hardcopy, and these hardcopies were searched for signatures in the present work. Figure 2.1 shows some of the ERS satellite tracks which can be acquired by TSS.

Figure 2.1 ERS SAR coverage within the TSS reception zone in 3 days with instrument always turned on.

2.3 Other constraints in use of AVHRR and SAR data

The main limiting factor in using AVHRR images for observation of the ocean surface in Norwegian waters is the frequent cloud cover. Even a thin or scattered cloud cover will make observations of the surface difficult or impossible. Off mid-Norway, an average cloud cover of more than 80% can be expected in long periods of the year. Especially in the autumn and winter seasons this area is frequently obscured by clouds.

SAR data, on the other hand, provide good quality images of the sea surface for all cloud and light conditions. But the capability of the SAR to observe the sea surface is dependent on a suitable wind speed interval. The best conditions for imaging is found for wind speeds roughly between 2 m/s and 8 m/s. Outside of this interval, the necessary modulation of the capillary waves to observe current signatures is usually not present. Too weak and too strong wind will result in very dark and very bright homogeneous images, respectively. This constraint limits the proportion of good observations to 30-50% of all SAR images available. The highest probability to find useful SAR images is in the summer (April - September), because then the winds are more gentle than in the winter season.

3. Previous SAR studies of ocean current and fronts

Theoretically, fronts are seen as sharply defined bright or dark lines on uniform background. The current gradients at the front will change the capillary waves at the front, and thus the measured backscatter signal. The front line is generally curved, and will often change between bright and dark segments along the front, due to angle dependencies of the effect.

In the real world, other factors will also affect the signal. Fronts are often associated with sea temperature changes that have an effect on the capillary waves through the boundary layer stability. Therefore, the change in backscatter across the front is often unsymmetrical.

Satellite SAR data collection over the oceans, shelf seas and coastal seas, has shown that many different geophysical parameters in the upper ocean and lower atmosphere can be observed. The main phenomena are: wind and its spatial variations, surface waves, fronts and eddies, internal waves, bottom topography in shallow water, oil spills and natural film. These phenomena are important for end users, particularly those operating in the marine environment, including; ocean and coastal navigation, shipping operations, offshore industry, including petroleum exploration and production, pollution control, fisheries and aquaculture, shore protection, monitoring and forecasting of weather and climate, coastguard, naval and military activities.

Under favourable wind conditions (wind speed between about 3 and 11m/s), satellite SAR may show features related to variations in ocean current (e.g. Fu and Stewart (1983)). Recent publications on this topic include (Johannessen et al., 1993a, 1993b, 1996a) and (Nilsson and Tildesley, 1995). Regions of current shear and current convergence or divergence can be expressed as bright or as dark features in a SAR image, depending on the sign of the various components of the current gradient, and the radar look direction with respect to the wind and current directions (Johannessen et al., 1996a).

3.1 ERS observations and modelling near Lindesnes

During the COASTWATCH'95 experiment, there was a number of SAR images where an obvious current front was detected together with a coincident infra-red (AVHRR) satellite image and shipborne ADCP current measurements.

In order to interpret SAR images of marine processes, it is necessary to have available SAR simulation models which can quantify values for relevant geophysical parameters, based on SAR data, and in situ atmospheric and oceanographic data. One of these models is the Environmental Research Institute of Michigan Ocean Model (EOM), which is an integrated hydrodynamic and electromagnetic model, that provides a full-spectrum solution to the wave action equation, using a two-scale composite radar backscatter model (Tanis et al., 1989).

The SAR image in Figure 3.1 shows a current front crossed during COASTWATCH'95 where in situ measurements, such as wind and currents, were obtained simultaneously with SAR coverage. EOM was run for a one-dimensional smoothed current data set based on ADCP measurements from 20m depth. The simulations of radar backscatter appeared to mainly reflect the relative speed of the wind with respect to the current. An ocean front, with a current

variation of the order of 50cm/s over a horizontal distance of 5km, showed up only weakly in the modelled backscatter. An attempt to account for wave breaking produced only a small effect. Model results with a simplified current field indicate that shear rates of nearly 10^{-2}s^{-1} (which are unrealistic) are required before the shear itself leads to a backscatter enhancement of the same order of magnitude as that actually observed. Therefore, model improvement is necessary.

Figure 3.1 ERS-2 SAR image from 11UTC on 27 Sep. 1997. The acoustic Doppler current profiler measurements in the 20m depth bin are shown using arrows along the ship track (south to north).

3.2 RADARSAT SAR observations near Haltenbanken

SAR data from the Canadian RADARSAT satellite is another potential source of information about ocean surface processes in the study area. This satellite has a number of modes, and can therefore obtain radar images with different swath widths and incidence angles. Many of these modes may be well suited for observations of ocean surface currents and eddies, as is shown in the example in Figure 3.2.

On 21 April 1996, 06:22GMT, the RADARSAT SAR sensor obtained an image covering about 130 by 101 km west of the Trøndelag coast of Norway. The image is located in waters of approximately 250m depth west of Haltenbanken, where some activity of current features is expected. A number of relatively faint ocean eddies and front features are seen in the western (far range) part of the scene, while the eastern part is almost featureless.

Figure 3.2 RADARSAT SAR image from 21 April 1996 NW of Haltenbanken(upper) and its location relative to the bottom topography (lower). Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

4. Data selection and processing

4.1 The area and time-period of image search

The area of search is defined to be between about 62°N and 68°N, and between the Norwegian coast and 0°E. Of special interest are areas where drilling for oil has been planned (e.g. Ormen Lange), and positions/sections where other current measurements have been made near-simultaneously (e.g. the Svinøy Section off Møre).

The time-period of search is defined from November 1996 until June 1998 (20 months).

Within these limits, a selection of SAR and AVHRR imagery was made based on a search of the hard-copy archives at TSS of AVHRR and SAR images. The location of the ERS-2 SAR images selected is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Selected ERS-2 SAR images (small boxes) and AVHRR images (large box) used in this study. Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

For SAR data, all processed scenes are available as hardcopies and as digital files in LRI³-format. TSS archives 10-15 scenes per day scattered over a large part of Northern Europe. The TSS archive only holds a small part of all the SAR data available from ESA, but it contains all images processed over the study area.

³ LRI - Low Resolution Image, pixel size approx. 100m in range and 80m in azimuth.

For AVHRR, several scenes for most days of interest are available for the study period both as hardcopy and as digital files in Sharp-format at TSS, with only a few days missing.

The selection was organised in 3 steps as follows:

1. All SAR hardcopy scenes with interesting current features (lines or eddies) visible were selected.
2. All AVHRR scenes from the same day as in step 1 showing some clear areas near the SAR scene(s) were selected.
3. Some additional AVHRR scenes showing large clear areas, or within a few days of the selection made in steps 1 and 2 were also selected.

A total of 63 SAR and 39 AVHRR scenes were selected for analysis. Consecutive ERS SAR scenes have been concatenated to form the 33 images (stripes) listed in Table 4.1. The location of all scenes is shown in Figure 4.1. For the AVHRR data sets, the same area were extracted from all images before analysis started, and this area is also marked in Figure 4.1. Unfortunately, only 6 AVHRR scenes were found to be of sufficiently high quality to be included in the study. On the other AVHRR images, clouds (not visible on the archive hardcopies) made mapping of ocean temperature ambiguous or impossible.

Table 4.1 Selected ERS-2 SAR scenes.

Image no.	Date	Time (UTC)	Number of scenes	Useful AVHRR image	Time difference AVHRR-SAR
1	10.Nov.1996	10:48	3		
2	29.Nov.1996	10:51	1		
3	19.Jan. 1997	10:49	1		
4	14.Mar.1997	10:51	3		
5	07.May.1997	10:54	3		
6	23.May.1997	10:51	1	Yes (23.May.1997, 12:24z)	+01 hours
7	01.Jun.1997	11:09	1	Yes (02.Jun.1997, 12:19z)	+25 hours
8	08.Jun.1997	10:48	2		
9	11.Jun.1997	10:54	4	Yes (10.Jun.1997, 12:29z)	-23 hours
10	19.Jun. 1997	21:32	1		
11	13.Jul. 1997	10:48	1		
12	16.Jul. 1997	10:54	4		
13	19.Jul.1997	10:59	3		
14	01.Aug.1997	10:51	3	Yes (01.Aug.1997, 03:08z)	-08 hours
15	30.Aug.1997	10:39	2		
16	24.Sep.1997	10:54	2	Yes (24.Sep.1997, 03:16z)	-07 hours
17	27.Sep.1997	11:00	2		
18	22.Dec.1997	10:57	2		
19	15.Jan.1998	21:32	1		
20	26.Jan.1998	10:57	1		
21	24.Feb.1998	10:45	2		
22	02.Mar.1998	10:57	2		
23	08.Mar.1998	11:09	2		
24	19.Apr.1998	10:49	1		
25	19.Apr.1998	10:47	1		
26	22.Apr.1998	10:54	2	Yes (21.Apr.1998, 06:26z)	-28 hours
27	05.May.1998	10:45	2		
28	08.May.1998	10:50	2		
29	16.May.1998	21:29	1		
30	30.May.1998	10:59	1		
31	12.Jun.1998	10:51	3		
32	12.Jun.1998	10:50	2		
33	24.Jun.1998	11:13	1		

4.2 Geometric and radiometric processing of ERS SAR data

The first step in the SAR processing is to perform geometric and radiometric correction, which include calibration, resulting in a uniform data set. SAR image pixels were resampled to 100 m square size, and adjacent scenes of 100 x 100 km concatenated to make larger images, called stripes, which each consisted of 1-4 scenes. Grid lines were overlaid with a grid accuracy of 1-2km.

The incidence angle, theta, is varying from 19.5° to 26.5° across the 100 km swath width of the image. Normalisation of the backscatter signal was performed crosstrack (in range direction), correcting for three effects: (1) antenna gain, (2) slant range and (3) sin(theta) (Laur et al., 1993, 1996). After this procedure, the SAR data are calibrated to an accuracy of approximately ±1.5dB. For image display purposes, the known variation of the backscatter with theta was also compensated (using the inverse sin(theta) to the 4th power), with reference to the midrange theta of 23°. At midrange, the conversion to the backscatter coefficient σ_0 , also called sigma-zero, is given in dB as follows:

$$\sigma_0 = 20 * \log (W) - 48$$

where W is the pixel value in the greytone image (8 bits).

All SAR images used in this study are presented in Chapter 5.

4.3 Feature classification in ERS SAR images

There are two major categories of processes which are observable in SAR images over ocean: (1) atmospheric boundary layer processes (wind, precipitation), and (2) ocean surface processes (surface waves, fronts, currents, sea ice). SAR can also provide information on specific features such as slicks, bathymetry and location of ships. In this study, only ocean current features are analysed.

There is a strong coupling of atmospheric and sea-surface processes observed in SAR images. Current fronts are observable because the wind generated capillary waves are modulated by the front. In moderate wind, most surface features are observable due to the wind modulation effect. In low wind and with biological surface material present characteristic for the summer period, most features are observable because slicks act as tracers of converging fronts, shears and of eddies.

There are some criteria which are used for separation of current fronts and eddies from other features with similar SAR signatures. The most important is to identify wind fronts which are characterised by a generally higher backscatter level on one side of the front compared to the other, while ocean fronts are characterised by line features (dark or bright) with a more homogenous background (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2 Idealised wind and current front signatures in SAR images.

Other criteria are related to the sizes and shapes of the fronts. Wind fronts are usually larger in extent and have less curvature than ocean fronts. Ocean fronts related to eddies may have a smaller scale and stronger curvature, but there are exceptions in the cases of rain showers and local wind gusts, where scales and shapes can be similar to ocean fronts.

Examples of wind and current fronts in ERS-1 SAR images are shown in Figure 4.3 and 4.4, along with the corresponding SAR backscatter profiles.

Figure 4.3 ERS-1 SAR image from 16 November 1991 showing a wind front in the Norwegian Sea (from Johannessen et al., 1994), and a backscatter profile along the thick black line.

Figure 4.4 NOAA AVHRR (left) and ERS-1 SAR image (right) from 3 October 1992 showing a current front off the western coast of Norway (from Johannessen et al., 1994), and a backscatter profile along the thick black line. Note that current fronts can appear both as peaks and troughs in backscatter profiles.

4.4 Relation between SAR backscatter and wind speed

The processing of the SAR images for this study has been optimised to extract surface features at wind speeds below 10m/s, where the wind signatures do not mask signatures caused by ocean fronts, eddies, internal waves and other oceanographic features. It is useful to relate SAR backscatter to wind speed using the CMOD4 algorithm, as shown in Figure 4.5.

CMOD4 is a standard model for expressing the backscatter as function of wind speed, wind direction, and incidence angle (Stoffelen and Anderson, 1993). It was developed for use with the ERS-1 scatterometer, but has also been found valid for use with ERS SAR. For practical studies of sea surface signatures, the range of SAR backscatter values is roughly between 10 and 130 in pixel value. Higher winds quickly masks the surface signatures.

The images are presented as greyscale images, with pixel values ranging from 0 to 255. The function between greyscale and pixel values is shown below each image. The linear black-to-white part (greytone scale) can vary from one image to another because it is optimised for each image to show the surface features as clearly as possible.

The white end of the graytone-scale corresponds roughly to the highest winds in the image. Its value is around 130 (-5dB) for a majority of the images. The variation of the white-end goes from 70 (-10dB) on the 01 June 1997 image, to 165 (-3dB) on the 19 April 1998 image. Assuming upwind, this corresponds to a maximum wind speed from approximately 2m/s to 10m/s.

It can be concluded that 10m/s represents roughly the high wind speed threshold which limits observation of ocean features in SAR images. In the case of crosswind, this limit may be somewhat conservative. Since many images have large areas of wind below 1.5m/s, the black end of the greytone-scale is often set to zero to show these low-wind areas. Examples of histograms of images used in the study are shown in Figure 4.6. Image no. 3 has a single peak histogram, while image no. 7 has two peaks, where the left peak represents the dark part of the image.

Figure 4.5 Relation given by CMOD4 between the windspeed and the pixelvalue/backscatter coefficient. The relation between the NERSC pixelvalue (0-255) and the backscatter coefficient is shown on the x-axis. Note that the ocean backscatter variation with SAR incidence angle has been normalised to midrange (23°). Upwind, $\phi=0^\circ$ is wind direction toward the sensor in range direction (which is perpendicular to the orbit). Backscatter for other wind directions can be approximated by assuming backscatter value $\sigma_0 \approx A + B * \sin(2*\phi)$ with A and B determined by the two curves. Backscatter is derived by $\sigma_0 = 20 * \log(W) - 47.4$, where W is the 8-bit pixel value. The thick dotted lines show roughly the interval in which wind speed can be derived from the SAR image.

Figure 4.6 Examples of histograms for some of the images used in this study. The range of pixel values between the SAR noise floor and the high end of wind speeds that are useful for showing ocean features on SAR is indicated with a dashed line in each histogram. The corresponding ERS-2 SAR images are shown to the right.

5. Analysis of signatures in the selected SAR and AVHRR images

5.1 Presentation of individual images

The selected SAR and near-simultaneous AVHRR images in Table 4.1 are here presented in chronological order, with a description of main features which can be observed in the images, such as wind streaks, current fronts and eddies, as well as sea surface temperature signatures. The SAR images consist of 1 to 4 scenes, while each AVHRR image consists of a subset of one scene, due to the much larger coverage area of this sensor. In some cases, it is possible to make a comparison between the SAR features seen by the ERS-2 satellite and the AVHRR SST features seen by the NOAA satellites. The cloud limitation of AVHRR data made it difficult to identify more than six cases where the two types of data were obtained at nearly the same time. These cases are listed in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Cases of near-simultaneous SAR and AVHRR images.

Image pair	ERS-2 Image	NOAA AVHRR Image	Time difference
6	23 May 1997, 10:51Z	23 May 1997, 12:24Z	+1.5 hour
7	01 June 1997, 11:09Z	02 June 1997, 12:19Z	+25 hours
9	11 June 1997, 10:54Z	10 June 1997, 12:29Z	-23 hours
14	01 August 1997, 10:51Z	01 August 1997, 03:08Z	-8 hours
16	24 September 1997, 10:54Z	24 September 1997, 03:16Z	-7 hours
26	22 April 1998, 10:54Z	21 April 1998, 06:26Z	-28 hours

The selected SAR images mainly cover low to moderate wind speed situations, up to about 10m/s. As mentioned previously, the possibility to detect ocean features decreases rapidly at wind speeds above 10m/s. The analysis of SAR images was made without meteorological information. In some cases meteorological information will be useful for support of the SAR interpretation, and this is recommended for the last phase of the study.

Image no.1
(SAR, 10.11.1996, 10:48 Z)

The image covers the shelf area east of Helland-Hansen and Ormen Lange. This is a characteristic image in a situation of unstable atmospheric boundary layer with rain showers and wind conditions which vary locally both in speed and direction. The wind speed varies from 2 - 3 m/s (dark areas) to above 10 m/s in the brightest areas. In such conditions it is difficult to identify ocean currents and frontal features.

Image no. 2 (SAR, 29.11.1996, 10:51 Z)

The image covers most of Ormen Lange. The image shows a characteristic mixture of darker and brighter areas occurring when the atmospheric boundary layer is unstable with convection causing locally varying surface winds. The image shows two weak wind fronts separating a low wind area in the centre from higher winds in the upper right and lower left corner. There is a thin bright line running north-south at about 6°E which is interpreted to be an ocean front.

Image no 3. (SAR, 19.01.1997, 10:49 Z)

The image covers the shelf area east of Ormen Lange. The image is obtained in a situation with stable atmospheric boundary layer and uniform weak wind field which does not show any wind fronts. The frontal features observed are all related to ocean fronts and eddies. The most pronounced meandering front running parallel to the coast is associated with the Norwegian Coastal Current.

Image no. 4
(SAR, 14.03.1997, 10:51 Z)

The image covers the area from Ormen Lange to Stad. It shows a more stable atmosphere south of 63°N compared to north of this latitude, where it is possible to identify some wind fronts and areas of lower (dark signature) and higher wind speeds (bright signature), respectively. South of 63°N several ocean fronts and eddy features are observed.

Image no. 5
(SAR, 07.05.1997, 10:54 Z)

The image covers the area from Ormen Lange to Stad. The whole image shows stable atmospheric conditions with low wind speeds. Several ocean frontal features and eddy structures are observed, especially north of 63°N. South of 62.5°N, smaller scale circulation features are visible as dark stripes caused by slicks. The darkest area just north of 62°N and east of 5°E is caused by wind shadowing near land, suggesting easterly winds.

Image no. 6a
(SAR, 23.05.1997, 10:51 Z)

The SAR image covers the shelf break area south of Ormen Lange. The main feature is the ocean front along 6°E. There is some small scale variability in the image indicating weak wind patterns.

Image no. 6b (AVHRR, 23.05.1997, 12:24 Z)

The AVHRR image shows cloudfree conditions along the coast and in the area covered by SAR (Image 6a). The surface temperature is in the range from 4° - 6°C with some weak gradients within the SAR area. The ocean front in the SAR image is not clearly identified in the AVHRR image, but there are filaments with different temperature which appear to be co-located with the SAR front. Small temperature gradients make it difficult to obtain clear features from the AVHRR image.

Image no. 7a
(SAR, 01.06.1997, 11:09 Z)

The SAR image is obtained in the Møre Vest area with depths from 1000 - 1500 m. The image is characteristic for a low wind situation, with wind speed not exceeding 2 - 3 m/s, combined with the presence of slicks, which generate a predominant dark signature in the image. Areas of slicks are frequently observed in the spring and summer time. The dark stripes of slicks create a clear picture of the circulation pattern in the area, showing several cyclonic eddies. The slicks are gradually vanishing north of 63°N. Note the jump in signature in the lower right corner from very dark (slick area) to bright (non-slick area).

Image no. 7b (AVHRR, 02.06.1997, 12:19 Z)

The AVHRR image is cloudfree over large parts of the study area south of 66°N. A core of warmer water (> 7°C, indicated by red) flows towards the coast north of Kristiansund, showing a number of eddies, meanders and filaments. In the area covered by SAR, there are filaments which correspond to the eddy structure observed in the SAR image. The transition zone from colder water in the western part of the SAR box to warmer water in the eastern part is not possible to identify in the SAR image.

Image no. 8 (SAR, 08.06.1997, 10:48 Z)

The image is located on the shallow area south of Vema/Nyk and west of Trænabanken. The image shows a complex mixture of atmospheric processes and ocean current features. The dark areas in the centre of the image are due to low winds and stripes of slicks. The upper part of the image shows atmospheric gravity waves, while the lower right part shows a puzzling pattern which is difficult to interpret. The other parts of the image show a number of eddies and other features reflecting the ocean circulation.

Image no. 9a
(SAR, 11.06.1997, 10:54 Z)

The SAR image covers the area from Helland Hansen, including Ormen Lange, and south to Stad. The image is taken in a low wind situation where the SAR signal is near the noise floor several places. The whole area which is 400 km long and 100 km wide is characterised by rich eddy activity displayed by the numerous stripes of slicks. The eddies seem to be uniformly distributed over the area.

Image no. 9b (AVHRR, 10.06.1997, 12:29 Z)

The AVHRR image shows cloudfree conditions in most of the area covered by SAR. Warmer water (>10°C) is flowing northwards along the coast. In the deep areas west of Ormen Lange, the temperature decreases to 5°C. The temperature gradients are now more well-defined, showing several eddies and filaments in the areas not covered by clouds. Some of the filaments in the SAR box correspond to surface current features in the SAR image.

Image no. 10 (SAR, 19.06.1997, 21:32 Z)

The image covers the Møre Basin between Møre Vest and Ormen Lange. The left part of the image is dominated by the effect of high wind speed which tends to mask structures at the surface. The presence of slicks in the right part, makes it possible to identify a cyclonic eddy which is 20 - 30 km in diameter and a few small scale eddies in the lower part of the image.

Image no. 11 (SAR, 13.07.1997, 10:48 Z)

The image covers the shallow area northeast of Ormen Lange. Most of the image shows surface current patterns which are visible as a consequence of the presence of slicks. The pattern displays the small scale variability or a form of turbulence of the surface velocity field. In the lower part of the image, the lack of slicks and/or a higher wind speed masks out surface current patterns.

Image no. 12
(SAR, 16.07.1997, 10:54 Z)

The image covers 400 km from east of Helland Hansen to Stad. This image is another example showing a complex mixture of atmospheric processes and surface current structures during low wind conditions. North of 63.5°N there is a number of elongated dark and bright features oriented in a SE - NW direction, which are due to wind variabilities. In addition, a pattern of surface currents including eddies and meanders is visible due to the presence of slicks. A train of internal waves is observed in the upper left part of the image. Eddy features are observed over Ormen Lange. South of 63.5°N there are fewer slick-covered areas, but where slicks are present circulation patterns can be identified. Near the coast some low wind areas are identified by dark signatures.

Image no. 13
(SAR, 19.07.1997, 10:59 Z)

The image covers the area from Helland Hansen towards Ormen Lange and partly overlaps with the image from three days earlier. East of 4°E the presence of slicks makes it possible to observe several cyclonic eddies. It is probable that the same eddies observed in the image three days before are also present in this image. For example, the well-defined cyclonic eddy centred at 64.25°N and 4.5°E on July 16 can have moved northwards to 64.75°N, into Helland Hansen, three days later. This is a propagation of 55 km in three days, corresponding to a mean velocity of 18 cm/s. But there are many cyclonic eddies in both images, and it is not obvious that the same eddies can be identified in the two images. In the lower left part of the image there is a dark region bounded by a local wind front and a slick front along the 3°E longitude.

Image no. 14a
(SAR, 01.08.1997, 10:51 Z)

The SAR image covers the shallow area east of Helland Hansen towards Ormen Lange. There is a pronounced wind front running north-south just west of 7°E. Some bands of slick are visible across this front, indicating surface current direction. The winds in the upper right part of the image are high enough to mask the surface signatures. Two clear cyclonic eddies with radius of 20 - 30 km are observable at 65.2°N and at 63.8°N. The other parts of the image show a number of small scale eddy features.

Image no. 14b (AVHRR, 01.08.1997, 03:08 Z)

The AVHRR image shows cloudfree conditions in large parts of the study area. The temperature gradients are now more pronounced compared to two months earlier, ranging from 4° to 10°C. These gradients show many eddy features, fronts and filaments, but the scales of the features in the AVHRR images are larger than the structures observed in the SAR image. A cyclonic eddy in the lower part of the SAR image corresponds to a filament of warmer water propagating northwards in the AVHRR image.

Image no. 15 (SAR, 30.08.1997, 10:39 Z)

The image covers the Haltenbanken area and shows a wind front running north-south which masks the ocean surface features in the right part of the image. West of about 9°E there is a mixture of atmospheric features (the dark area centred at 64.5°N with a wave pattern which can be atmospheric waves) and a number of smaller scale frontal features indicating current directions. The bright areas west of the front can also be caused by rain showers which dampen the capillary waves.

Image no. 16a (SAR, 24.09.1997, 10:54 Z)

The SAR image covers the area from Ormen Lange to Stad. The image shows a weak and uniform wind field which allows observation of many current fronts and eddies south of 63°N.

Image no. 16b (AVHRR, 24.09.1997, 03:16 Z)

The AVHRR image shows lower temperatures and smaller gradients compared to earlier in the summer. Characteristic surface temperature is 4° - 6°C. Eddy features can be seen both in the SAR area, including Ormen Lange, and further north in Helland Hansen area. The eddy in the centre of the SAR box observed in the AVHRR image corresponds to eddy features observed in the SAR image.

Image no. 17 (SAR, 27.09.1997, 11:00 Z)

The image covers the area southwest of Ormen Lange, showing several very clear current fronts and eddy features south of 63N. The eddies are observable in the same area as three days earlier, but recognition is not possible due to rapid change in the shape and location of the eddies over a three-day period. The main fronts are oriented in northeasterly direction, parallel to the bathymetry. Most of the eddy features are found around 62.5N, which is just over the shelf break.

Image no. 18 (SAR, 22.12.1997, 10:57 Z)

SAR images during low wind conditions showing frontal features have not been found in the period from late September to late December. This SAR image from 22 December, covering the area from Helland Hansen towards Ormen Lange, shows a number of eddy features in most of the image except in the upper part where the wind is higher. There is a wind front just south of 65N. South of this front the atmospheric stability appears to be low, giving rise to a number of small scale features which can be attributed to variable surface wind and rain showers.

Image no. 19 (SAR, 15.01.1998, 21:32 Z)

The image is taken over the shallow area northwest of Stad. The image shows several current frontal structures oriented in a northeasterly direction, parallel to the bathymetry. Internal waves are observable north of 62.5°N and west of 4°E, which is near the shelf break. The internal waves are propagating south-westwards.

Image no. 20 (SAR, 26.01.1998, 10:57 Z)

The image is taken west of Stad. The most well-defined frontal feature is a current front directed in a northwesterly direction, south of 62°N, in shallow waters not far from land. There is also a frontal feature along the left side of the image, which is probably attributed to wind variability.

Image no. 21 (SAR, 24.02.1998, 10:45 Z)

There are several well-defined curved-shaped current fronts in the lower right part of the image, located northwest of Frøya and Smøla (marked by the white contour line). The bright spots outside the islands are caused by wave breaking in shallow areas. There are also some wind front structures running in a northwesterly direction.

Image no. 22 (SAR, 02.03.1998, 10:57 Z)

The image covers an area just south of Ormen Lange. The upper part of the image shows a pattern of small scale wind variability which is a characteristic for an unstable atmospheric boundary layer. Towards south, the stability increases allowing current frontal features to be observable. North of 62.5°N and west of 4°E a train of internal waves propagating westwards is evident.

Image no. 23 (SAR, 08.03.1998, 11:09 Z)

The image covers an area southwest of the Møre Basin. Except for the dark and bright areas centred around 63°N and 0.5°E most of the features in the image are attributed to current frontal features. The main features are oriented in northeasterly direction, along the mean current, while there are some shorter features oriented perpendicular to the mean current.

Image no. 24 (SAR, 19.04.1998, 10:49 Z)

The image, taken over shallow waters west of Kristiansund, shows a typical low wind situation combined with the presence of slicks which makes the surface current pattern visible. The eddy features have a small scale (< 5km) and no clear current fronts are evident. The wind speed increases towards the north, which causes the surface signatures to disappear north of about 63.3°N.

Image no. 25 (SAR, 19.04.1998, 10:47 Z)

This image is from the same orbit as the previous one, but taken further north, roughly between 67°N and 68°N, northeast of Vema/Nyk. The image shows frontal features which are caused by currents, but also wind features such as in the lower part of the image, between 9°E and 10°E.

Image no. 26a (SAR, 22.04.1998, 10:54 Z)

The SAR image covers the Ormen Lange field and is dominated by high winds in the lower left part, shown as the bright area of the image. The other parts of the image show the surface current pattern in detail due to the presence of slicks and low wind. Many cyclonic eddies are visible. The most pronounced eddy is centred at 63.5°N and 5.3°E, which is in Ormen Lange.

Image no. 26b (AVHRR, 21.04.1998, 06:26 Z)

The AVHRR image shows several smaller scale filaments and features within the SAR box which correspond to some of the current patterns in the SAR image. Especially, the cyclonic eddy in the centre of the SAR box is well-defined on both the SAR and AVHRR image and covers the Ormen Lange field.

Image no. 27 (SAR, 05.05.1998, 10:45 Z)

The image is taken on Haltenbanken northeast of Ormen Lange. The upper left part of the image is dominated by higher wind which masks most of the surface features, but not all. For example, there is a strong current front at 64.9°N and 7.5°E. The right part of the image has less wind and more slicks which makes surface current patterns visible. At 64.2°N and 7.5°E there is a well-defined anticyclone surrounded by numerous smaller scale eddy features. The large dark area in the lower part of the image is due to very low wind speed (< 2-3m/s) which also masks out slicks and current features.

Image no. 28 (SAR, 08.05.1998, 10:50 Z)

This SAR image covers the area west of Trønabanken and east of Vema/Nyk. The image shows strong convection patterns due to atmospheric instability in the western part, generating high local winds with rain showers and well-defined wind fronts. The areas outside the convection cells show typical surface current patterns, except in some dark areas with very low winds.

Image no. 29 (SAR, 16.05.1998, 21:29 Z)

The image covers the area northwest of Stad. There is a pattern of wind stripes across the image oriented in a northeasterly direction, parallel to the coast. The dark areas near land are caused by wind shadowing (local low winds). South of 62.4°N, there are several current features with a characteristic curved shape. The long, narrow and dark feature at 62.2°N just west of 5°E can be an oil slick.

Image no. 30 (SAR, 30.05.1998, 10:59 Z)

The image covers the Helland Hansen field, and shows many frontal features associated with currents and eddies. No wind features are observed.

Image no. 31
(SAR, 12.06.1998, 10:51 Z
- southern image)

The image covers the area from Ormen Lange field and south to Stad. Near the coast there are low-wind areas and some convection cells with high local winds, rain cells and wind fronts. Further west there are many frontal and small scale eddy features.

Image no. 32 (SAR, 12.06.1998, 10:50 Z - northern image)

The image covers the Vema/Nyk field and shows a pronounced cyclonic eddy centred at 67.4°N and 8°E with a diameter of 20 - 30 km, which can be caused by a cyclone in the atmosphere. The area surrounding the eddy shows local wind variability, which is characteristic for an unstable atmospheric boundary layer. South of the eddy, there are several frontal features associated with currents and generally higher wind speed.

Image no. 33 (SAR, 24.06.1998, 11:13 Z)

The image covers an area on the Vøring Plateau, southwest of Gjallar Ridge, showing a larger ocean eddy centered at 66.5°N and 2.3°E. A possible wind front extends across the image, from left to right. The lower part of the image has higher wind speed which masks the surface features.

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5. Analysis of signatures in the selected SAR and AVHRR images

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5.2 *Graphic display of frontal features*

For each SAR image, currents, frontal and eddy features are identified and drawn on a map together with the 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m depth contours. Red lines mark current, eddy and frontal features, while blue lines indicate wind fronts. This analysis allows a comparison of current features with bathymetry and geographic area.

For the AVHRR images, the relative temperature differences are displayed where blue indicates colder water and red indicates warmer water. Gray areas indicate cloud cover.

Figure 5.1 Overview of current fronts and eddy features from SAR and AVHRR images. Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

Figure 5.1 (continued) Overview of current fronts and eddy features from SAR and AVHRR images. Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

Figure 5.1 (continued) Overview of current fronts and eddy features from SAR and AVHRR images. Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

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Figure 5.1 (continued) Overview of current fronts and eddy features from SAR and AVHRR images. Contours for depths 500m, 1000m, 2000m and 3000m are shown.

5.3 Discussion

The number of useful SAR images selected for this project is 33, spanning a period of 20 months. The study area is roughly covered with 8 descending SAR tracks, which are repeated every 35 days (the satellite orbit repeat period). But the SAR instrument is not turned on for every orbit. The SAR archive at TSS contained about 70 images in the study area. Therefore, about 45% of all available SAR images contain information on eddies, fronts and surface current features. The other 55% had no such features, mainly due to high wind and other atmosphere effects.

The selection of imagery of the study area has been made in a non-random way: In west and north areas, fewer scenes were available (processed) than in east and south areas. Also, the selection of scenes was made primarily for the continental slope areas in Figure 1.1, so coastal areas are under-represented. As seen from Figure 5.1, eddies, fronts and current patterns are found at most locations where SAR data have been obtained. Since the spatial distribution of observation is non-homogeneous, we have estimated for each square of 0.5° latitude and 1° longitude: number of images, number of observations, and relative occurrence of observations (Figure 5.2). The relative occurrence is total number of observed fronts and eddy features in each $0.5^\circ \times 1^\circ$ square divided by number of SAR images within a square. The relative occurrence of features shows that the most intense front and eddy areas are northwest of Stad and along the shelf break north of 62.5°N .

Figure 5.2 Spatial distribution of SAR images (left), fronts observed in them (middle) and the relative frequency of front occurrence (right).

For only six cases, good quality AVHRR images taken within one day of a SAR image were found. The cases of joint SAR-AVHRR image pairs were all obtained in spring and summer situations where slick-features dominated. In the AVHRR images, many eddy signatures were also observed outside of the SAR coverage box, some following the continental slope, but others also in other positions.

The SAR ocean surface features can be divided into two main groups:

1. Fronts or eddies are seen as curved dark or bright current lines without occurrence of slicks. The background may have the same backscatter on both sides, or it may be brighter on one side. Lines are caused by zones of current shear and convergence/divergence, which affect the capillary waves and thereby the SAR backscatter.
2. Dark slicks show surface current patterns including eddies without clear fronts. Biological surface material acts as tracers for the water motion, especially in the spring and summer.

The main results of image analysis are summarised in Table 5.1. For ocean fronts, the number of observations in each image, and the range in length and orientation are indicated. The frontal signature (brighter or darker than surrounding backscatter) is shown, indicating that bright and dark signatures are equally well represented. For current patterns due to slicks, without clear fronts, it is estimated if there is a turbulent current field and/or if there is a predominant direction of the current. For both fronts and current patterns it is estimated how many eddies (cyclonic and anticyclonic) are observed and what is their horizontal size.

One main question is to estimate how well the surface current features observed by SAR images represent the currents observed by in situ measurements. This will be studied in a comparison between satellite data and in situ current measurements.

Table 5.1 Features seen in the SAR images.

Image no.	Image date	Ocean fronts					Current pattern without fronts		Eddies			Comments
		# of fronts	length (km)	orientation	bright front	dark front	turbulent field	orientation	# cyclonic	# anti-cyclonic	scale (km)	
1	10.11.96	no					no		-	-		only atmospheric features
2	29.11.96	1	30	N-S	X		no		-	-		mainly atmospheric features
3	19.01.97	15-20	5-100	NW-SE SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		
4	14.03.97	8-12	5-80	SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		
5	07.05.97	10-20	5-30	all	many	a few	no	EW + all	3 - 5	1	5 - 30	
6	23.05.97	3-5	10-50	N-S	X	X	no		2	-	10 - 20	
7	01.06.97	3-5	10-20	N-S	-	X	yes	all	3 - 4	1	10 - 30	
8	08.06.97	2-3	10-20	E-W	X	X	yes	all	7 - 8	1 - 2	5 - 30	
9	11.06.97	no					yes	all	8 - 10	3 - 4	10 - 40	eddies visible due to slicks
10	19.06.97	no					yes	all	3	-	5 - 40	most of image covered by winds
11	13.07.97	no					yes	all	yes	yes	> 5	turbulent eddy field dominates
12	16.07.97	4-6	20-30	N-S E-W	-	X	yes	all	6 - 7	1 - 2	10 - 50	well-defined eddies, internal waves
13	19.07.97	3-5	20-50	N-S E-W	-	X	little		5 - 6	-	10 - 40	well-defined eddies
14	01.08.97	3-5	20-30	N-S	X	X	yes	all	3 - 4	-	20 - 30	also small scale eddies < 5 km
15	30.08.97	10-15	20-50	N-S	many	-	no	SE - NW	2 - 3	-	5 - 10	
16	24.09.97	8-10	20-40	all	X	X	no		4 - 5	-	10 - 20	
17	27.09.97	10-12	10-100	SW-NE	X	X	little	S - N	3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
18	22.12.97	> 20	10-50	all	X	X	little	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	
19	15.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	little		1	-	20	
20	26.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	no		-	-		
21	24.02.98	5-6	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		-	-		
22	02.03.98	4-5	10-40	all	X	-	no		-	-		internal waves
23	08.03.98	6-8	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		1	-	20	
24	19.04.98	no					yes	all	5 - 6	-	5 - 20	
25	19.04.98	4-5	10-50	all	X	X	no		3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
26	22.04.98	no					yes	all	6 - 7	-	10 - 30	cyclonic eddy also visible in AVHRR image
27	05.05.98	4-5	10-30	E-W			little	all	5 - 6	1 - 2	10 - 20	
28	08.05.98	no					yes	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	convective cells
29	16.05.98	2-3	20-30	NW-SE	X	X	little	EW	2 - 3	1	5 - 30	possible oil slick
30	30.05.98	4-5	20-50	NW-SE	X	-	little	SW-NE	2 - 3	-	10 - 20	
31	12.06.98	3-4	20-30	all	X	X	yes	all	-	-		internal waves
32	12.06.98	4-5	20-50	ALL			no		1	0	30	eddy can also be wind cyclone
33	24.06.98	no					little		0	1	30	

6. Conclusions

In low and moderate wind situations, ocean fronts, current patterns and eddy signatures are frequently found in SAR images. The current patterns due to slicks show turbulent fields or well defined eddies with length scale from 10 to 50km. Fronts and eddies occur both over the shelf area, over the shelf slope, and further out in deep areas. Current patterns due to slicks are most frequently observed in spring and summer.

At higher wind speeds, i.e. above about 10m/s, the surface signatures in SAR images due to currents and ocean fronts will be masked. Also in extremely low wind situations (wind speed < 2-3m/s) the signatures disappear, but this situation occurs more rarely. In cases when the wind speed is between 3 and 10m/s, properly calibrated and enhanced SAR images can be used to separate ocean surface features from atmospheric features such as wind fronts and convection cells.

In this study 33 SAR images were selected from the archive at Tromsø Satellite Station. The analysis showed that 25 images contained approximately 150 observations of ocean fronts, while 8 images showed no fronts (April-June images). The length of the observed ocean fronts varied from 5 to 100km, with a typical length of 20-40km. In 16 images, the ocean fronts had 1-2 predominant directions (NW-SE and SW-NW), while the remaining 9 images showed fronts oriented in all directions. For the observed ocean fronts, bright and dark signatures were equally represented.

Current patterns without ocean fronts, i.e. due to slicks, were observed in 19 of the 33 images. The typical pattern was that of a turbulent surface velocity field or as well defined eddies rotating cyclonically or anticyclonically. These current patterns were orientated in all directions, and were most predominant in April-August.

Eddies were observed in 25 of the 33 SAR images, and included about 80 cyclonic eddies and about 10 anticyclonic eddies. The typical horizontal scale was 10-30km. Eddy-like features with a diameter of less than 5km were classified as turbulent surface velocity fields. A SAR image from 16 July 1997 (Image no.12) contained a well-defined cyclonic eddy centered at 64.25°N and 4.5°E, which probably moved northwards to 64.75°N, into Helland Hansen, three days later (Image no. 13). This corresponds to a mean propagation speed of 18cm/s. Near simultaneous observations of eddies in SAR and AVHRR images were made in 2 cases (Image 14a-b and 16a-b, acquired on 1 August 1997 and 24 September 1997, respectively).

Combining the analysis of SAR and AVHRR images with the bottom topography in the study area, showed that the maximum occurrence of fronts and eddies is found along the shelf break (i.e. the 500-1000m isobath line). Between 62.5°N-63.0°N and 3°E-4°E, 25 observations were made in 6 images, while between 63.0°N-63.5°N and 5°E-6°E, 29 observations were made in 6 images. NW of Stad, between 62.0°N-62.5°N and 4°E-5°E, 30 observations were made in 9 images.

However, with a swath width of only 100km for the ERS SAR images, the spatial statistics of ocean current features cannot be as representative as it could have been with use of 500km wide RADARSAT SAR images. On the other hand, the maps showing the surface features found in the images selected for this study (Figure 5.1), provide valuable information on the

variability of the location of these features, when taking into account the fairly small number of SAR images used in this study. These maps can also be used in later studies of spatial distribution of current features and eddies, for instance to augment the statistics derived from other types of satellite data.

Another possibility is to use RADARSAT SAR data, where more frequent coverage is possible, due to their much wider swaths. However, these data are far more expensive, and careful planning will be required to obtain an optimal temporal and spatial coverage of the study area.

The most interesting part of this study remains to be done. That is to compare satellite observations with in situ current measurements and modelling results.

7. References

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